

Analysis of the Impact of Employment Internship Practice on the Training of Engineering Students

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The study on Professional Internship I of Industrial Civil Engineering students at the Universidad Arturo Prat reveals that this formative instance is fundamental to the development of both technical and transversal competencies necessary for their labor market insertion. Evaluations provided by direct supervisors show that most students obtain high ratings in criteria such as professionalism, workplace relationships, and initiative, which indicates effective integration into the work environment and a proactive attitude toward assigned responsibilities. Regarding technical knowledge, the majority demonstrate an adequate command of content, although some students exhibit areas that require improvement. The sectors where professional internships are concentrated are mainly commerce and education, accounting for almost half of the experiences, while sectors such as mining, fishing, and transportation have low representation. This concentration suggests the need to promote greater diversification of internship opportunities to enrich training and expand employability prospects. The main contribution of the study lies in evidencing the importance of professional internships as a bridge between academic training and the world of work, integrating employer evaluations to adjust and improve the curriculum. For future projections, it is recommended to conduct longitudinal follow-up comparing the evolution of competencies across different internship stages, and to collect students' direct perceptions to complement quantitative data, which will enable optimization of the formative experience and strengthen students' professional preparation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to the Self-Evaluation Report of the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Universidad Arturo Prat, the Industrial Civil Engineer is described as a professional prepared to perform in both the administrative and productive areas of any company, especially in management functions. Their training qualifies them to develop, direct, control, evaluate, and generally plan all types of engineering projects, participating in both the technical and administrative areas, coordinating resources in order to contribute to the social and economic development of the region and the country. This professional is particularly prepared to apply their knowledge to the development of the national industry. In addition, they are qualified to develop and disseminate scientific and technological knowledge through teaching and research. They may also practice the profession independently or as entrepreneurs, in industrial and business activities in general, as well as in public institutions dedicated to planning, research, and control.

In order to train future industrial civil engineers, the program includes a Curricular Training Plan, also referred to as a Study Plan, with a duration of five years and consisting of 57 courses. Of these, 51 are mandatory and six are electives, distributed into three general education courses and three specialization courses. The plan also includes two professional internships that constitute part of the mandatory curriculum.

The structure of the study plan is organized into three stages that define the formative path: Basic Sciences courses, Engineering Sciences courses, and Specialization courses. These courses comprise both theoretical and practical activities, through laboratories and workshops.

Professional internships constitute an essential component of the training plan because they facilitate student engagement with the work environment. They allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in real contexts, strengthening technical competencies and key professional skills. In the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Universidad Arturo Prat, internships also serve as a mechanism for feedback regarding students' level of preparation in relation to labor market demands.

Specifically, Professional Internship I aims primarily to introduce the student to the work environment. At this stage, the student focuses on observing and recording the operation of the company, identifying its organizational structure, recognizing hierarchies, and becoming familiar with internal procedures, all through the analysis and application of the knowledge acquired at that point in their training. This curricular activity requires a duration of 360 chronological hours.

The expected Learning Outcomes for Professional Internship I are:

- Analyze organizational reality in relation to the functioning of the company.
- Provide support in technical and/or administrative tasks within the company.
- Apply concepts of effective oral and written communication in activities inherent to their functions within the company.

Additionally, this internship seeks to strengthen the following generic and specific competencies of the graduate profile:

Generic competencies:

- Communicates ideas, arguments, and knowledge clearly and effectively, both orally and in writing, using appropriate means and adapting to the characteristics of the situation and the audience.
- Uses information and communication technologies adequately and appropriately, as required for professional and social engagement, enabling lifelong learning.
- Actively integrates into work teams to achieve common objectives with other individuals, areas, or organizations, adequately addressing conflicts that are part of these processes.

Specific competencies:

- Applies fundamentals of Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Engineering Sciences for the analysis and development of solutions to engineering problems.
- Applies strategies to deepen their scientific and technological knowledge related to the various disciplines that support the profession and that may be useful.

This study focuses on the analysis of Professional Internship I, which may be completed by students who are in the sixth level of the program, considering that it is structured into 10 semesters (levels). The objective of the study is to evaluate the impact of this internship on the students' training process, identifying the factors that influence this process and, based on the analysis of performance during the internship, to propose recommendations for improving the Curricular Training Plan. The period considered for this analysis includes internships conducted between January 2022 and July 2024.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter develops the theoretical framework that underpins the research, aimed at understanding the formative processes that occur during the transition from higher education to the world of work. In particular, it examines the dynamics of experiential learning, socialization in professional contexts, and the formative value of professional internships in shaping the identity and performance of future professionals.

The chapter begins with a review of educational models centered on experience as the driver of meaningful learning, followed by an analysis of organizational and professional socialization processes that shape behavior, attitudes, and adaptation within organizations. Finally, it explores the role of professional internships as privileged spaces for consolidating technical, social, and ethical competencies in real-world contexts.

2.1 Experiential Learning and Professional Socialization

[1] argues that the modern educator does not teach but guides learning. They do not provide knowledge, but skillfully direct learners toward acquiring it. They do not transmit preconstructed truths but lead toward discovery. This perspective highlights the need to break with traditional educational paradigms, promoting a conception of learning as a dynamic, bidirectional process between experience and theory [2]. From this perspective, experience alone does not generate knowledge: the individual must modify their cognitive strategies for learning to occur. Experience acquires meaning when it is articulated with previous knowledge and when conceptual scaffolding is constructed that allows new knowledge to be applied to diverse contexts [3].

In this line, the experiential learning model proposed by [4] suggests that effective learning occurs through a cycle composed of four stages: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Professional internships integrate directly into this model because they provide students with authentic, concrete experiences from which they can develop reflective observations about organizational challenges, dynamics, and contexts. This interaction with the professional environment enables students to confront theory with practice, consolidate their understanding, and acquire new competencies.

Professional internships also play a fundamental role in the socialization of individuals within the labor sphere. Through them, students are exposed to organizational culture, expected roles, teamwork dynamics, and the development of contact networks. This process falls within the framework of Organizational Socialization, understood as the learning through which individuals adapt to an organization by internalizing its values, norms, and expected behaviors [5]. Complementarily, the concept of Professional Socialization

refers to the complex and continuous process through which an individual becomes an active member of a specific profession. From sociology and social psychology, this process has been described as a long-term phenomenon through which individuals learn to participate in social and professional life, adopting norms and performing meaningful roles [6, 7].

In the current context, marked by globalization and accelerated technological advancements, the demands placed on professionals have evolved. As stated in [8], engineering—a discipline with centuries of history—must now respond to new social, scientific, and technological challenges. In this scenario, employment internship practices acquire a crucial role in strengthening key competencies before the definitive entry into the labor market. In particular, a growing emphasis has been observed on the so-called soft skills related to communication, collaborative work, and leadership, in contrast to the traditional focus solely on technical competencies.

Experiential learning and professional socialization in engineering, as noted in [9], are essential for developing practical skills and creating connections with the labor environment, especially in the post-pandemic context. Activities such as research projects, virtual simulations, and multidisciplinary teamwork enable students to apply knowledge in real or simulated situations, strengthening problem-solving and decision-making capacities [10]. Furthermore, participation in international projects and virtual communities of practice facilitates socialization with professionals and peers, promoting interaction, collaborative work, and integration into professional culture, resulting in better preparation for current labor market challenges [11–13].

2.2 Socialization in the Professional Context

Contemporary education demands new ways of addressing teaching and learning, where student protagonism and the connection between theory and practice play a central role. This section examines pedagogical approaches that emphasize experiential learning as an active, reflective, and situated process. Within this framework, the contributions of authors such as Kolb are analyzed and linked to professional internships as spaces for knowledge construction and skill development in real contexts.

2.2.1 Organizational Socialization

Beyond mastering technical content, entering the labor market involves undergoing processes of adaptation and social integration. This section addresses the different dimensions of socialization in professional environments, distinguishing between organizational socialization—related to learning norms, dynamics, and culture inherent to an organization—and professional socialization, which relates to constructing an identity within a disciplinary community. Additionally, it examines professional internships as key instances to support these processes and prepare students for the challenges of professional work.

From entry into an organization to the moment a person leaves it, individuals go through a complex process of adaptation and learning that involves integrating into a new lifestyle with its particular rhythms, relationships, and demands. Although each organization has its own characteristics—some barely noticeable, others markedly different—evidence suggests that no work environment leaves its members indifferent. In this context, the concept of organizational socialization arises, understood as the process through which individuals acquire the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to perform a role within an organization [14].

This process does not take place in an institutional or merely functional vacuum; it is profoundly influenced by the social relationships that individuals establish with colleagues, superiors, subordinates, and other actors within the work environment. These interactions allow individuals to interpret everyday situations, facilitating effective integration that may culminate in a sense of achievement and competence or, conversely, in perceptions of failure and inadequacy. The quality of organizational socialization directly

impacts institutional stability and productivity: a smooth transition between generations of workers ensures continuity of the organizational mission, particularly in relatively stable contexts.

In this sense, [15] developed the Organizational Socialization Inventory (OSI), a quantitative instrument designed to evaluate employee socialization in diverse work environments. The OSI is based on four sociopsychological factors that influence perceptions of socialization: training received, understanding of such training, support from colleagues, and prospects. In its original study—which involved 360 workers from different sectors and hierarchical levels in Singapore—a 20-item questionnaire using a seven-point Likert scale was developed, demonstrating high reliability and validity. Since then, the OSI has been validated in multiple studies and has proven useful in relation to variables such as leadership [16], job performance, emotional intelligence [17], and organizational commitment [18], among others.

2.2.2 Professional Socialization

Professional socialization complements organizational processes by referring to the transformation through which an individual becomes recognized as a legitimate member of a professional community. This process has technical, moral, and cultural dimensions, deeply influencing the professional and ethical behavior of those who undergo it.

According to the conceptual analysis by [19], based on Walker and Avant's eight-step approach, professional socialization is a nonlinear, continuous, interactive, and transformative process shaped by the internalization of the specific culture of the profession. This definition also acknowledges that the process is influenced by individual, organizational, and contextual factors, and that its evolution is both personal and psychosocial.

This type of socialization does not occur solely in the workplace; it often begins during formal education, when students begin to incorporate norms, values, and ways of thinking characteristic of their discipline. It is a key dimension in the consolidation of professional identity and in the preparation needed to face the ethical and technical challenges of professional practice.

2.2.3 The Professional Internship as a Formative Bridge

In this context, professional internships constitute an essential component of the higher education training process because they articulate academic knowledge with the world of work. Beyond the development of technical skills, internships provide an opportunity to apply knowledge in real contexts, with concrete problems and diverse actors, enabling a deeper and more meaningful understanding of the profession [20].

This notion has been addressed from several theoretical perspectives: psychosocial [21], sociocultural, ontological [22], human development [23], and curricular [24]. All perspectives highlight that professional internships not only strengthen technical competencies but also enhance students' personal and professional development, consolidating the transition from learner to emerging professional.

Professional internships in engineering are fundamental because they enable students to apply theoretical knowledge acquired in academic settings to real work environments, fostering the development of essential practical competencies and skills for their professional performance [25]. Likewise, they contribute to the formation of professional identity, promote an understanding of sector dynamics, and facilitate network development that may be useful in future careers [26]. Internships also help students grasp the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and teamwork—critical skills in addressing complex challenges engineers face in professional practice [27].

[28] adds that the importance of professional internships in engineering education lies in the opportunity to acquire practical experience, develop field-specific skills, and strengthen the understanding of theoretical

concepts applied in real situations. These internships facilitate the integration of academic training with labor market needs, allowing students to become familiar with industry dynamics and demands, improve employability, and foster competencies such as problem-solving, teamwork, and project management [29]. Moreover, they help engineers contextualize technical knowledge in concrete scenarios, which is essential for their professional development and for responding effectively to labor and social challenges [30].

3. METHOD

This section presents the methodological framework that supported the development of the research, describing the adopted approach, study design, participants, instruments, and techniques used for data collection and analysis, and the ethical considerations applied. This methodological approach allowed for the collection of reliable and pertinent information to fulfill the study's objectives, ensuring the rigor and validity of the obtained results.

3.1 Research Approach

This study adopted a quantitative approach, which, in the words of [31], is a research methodology focused on the collection and analysis of numerical data to identify patterns, relationships, and trends in a specific population or phenomenon. [32] adds that this approach uses instruments such as surveys, questionnaires, and standardized tests to obtain objective and quantifiable data, which are subsequently analyzed statistically.

3.2 Research Design

Given the data collection process in this study, the most appropriate research design was the cross-sectional design, a methodological strategy consisting of collecting data and information at a specific moment in time, allowing the analysis of a population or phenomenon at a single point [33]. This type of design, according to [34], is useful for describing characteristics, determining prevalence, or exploring relationships between variables at a given moment, providing an instantaneous view of reality that allows comparisons between different groups or segments within the sample.

3.3 Participants

The target population of the study consisted of students enrolled in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University who completed Professional Internship I during the period between January 2022 and July 2024, totaling 173 individuals. From this total, an effective sample of 31 students who voluntarily responded to the survey was obtained.

The sample corresponds to a non-probabilistic intentional sampling method [35], given that participation was voluntary and targeted at those who had completed the internship within the analyzed period. Despite representing a reduced percentage of the total population, the responses obtained...

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

In order to evaluate the impact of Professional Internship I on the educational process of students enrolled in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University, an instrument was designed to gather relevant information from the perspective of the students who completed this curricular activity. This instrument considers five fundamental dimensions that allow for the assessment of both technical

performance and the development of soft skills and professional attitudes, in accordance with the graduate profile of the program.

- Professionalism: Demonstrates commitment and responsibility toward assigned duties. Likewise, complies with the organization's regulations and with the instructions of supervisors, behaving ethically and professionally in every action.
- Quality of Work: Demonstrates that the execution of assigned tasks and the work performed meet the expectations established by supervisors.
- Technical Knowledge: Demonstrates the ability to apply engineering concepts and tools in critical analysis and in developing solutions to problems posed during the internship. Additionally, can communicate ideas, arguments, and knowledge clearly and effectively, both orally and in writing.
- Work Relationships: Demonstrates willingness to collaborate with the organization and with co-workers. Likewise, shows the ability to work effectively in a team.
- Initiative: Demonstrates proactivity in addressing and resolving situations arising in the course of their duties. Also shows interest and willingness to learn, progress, and improve.

The survey was structured using the Google Forms platform. The instrument consisted of 14 questions, of which 6 were aimed at gathering general information about the student, such as the semester in which the internship was completed, the industry of the organization, and the geographic region of the company. The remaining 7 questions focused on measuring perceptions of the internship process using a 1-to-7 Likert scale, which allowed for evaluating the degree of agreement or satisfaction regarding key aspects such as awareness of internship objectives, satisfaction with the technical knowledge acquired, and receipt of the required insurance coverage. Finally, an open-ended question was included to collect comments and suggestions from students concerning potential improvements to the professional internship process.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis of the data collected was conducted through a quantitative approach, using descriptive statistics as the primary technique. The information was obtained through a structured survey, which included questions using a 1-to-7 Likert scale designed to measure the degree of agreement or satisfaction of students with different aspects of the professional internship process. The data were organized and processed in an electronic spreadsheet, which allowed for the systematization of responses and facilitated their interpretation. For each item assessed, absolute and relative frequencies were calculated according to response categories, enabling the identification of general trends in students' perceptions. The results were graphically represented using bar charts.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

In the methodological design of this research, compliance with fundamental ethical principles outlined in [36] was ensured, beginning with the acquisition of informed consent from participants, who were properly informed about the objectives, procedures, and potential risks or benefits of the study to ensure voluntary and informed participation. Additionally, confidentiality and anonymity of all collected information were guaranteed, protecting participants' privacy at all times.

Precautions were taken to avoid causing discomfort or harm, as indicated in [37], implementing measures that ensured participants' well-being throughout the process. The selection of participants was conducted in accordance with the principles of justice and equity, avoiding any form of discrimination. Finally, transparency in the presentation of results was guaranteed, and all regulations and requirements

established by ethics committees were met, thereby ensuring the integrity and ethical responsibility of the research [38].

3.7 Procedure

The information collected through the assessment instrument, along with the database of students who completed Professional Internship I, was systematically organized and analyzed with the objective of facilitating its understanding and interpretation. This process included a series of key stages aimed at ensuring the accuracy, relevance, and clarity of the results obtained.

First, the responses were coded, which allowed the information to be structured with a specific focus and facilitated comparisons among different cases. In the case of qualitative responses, a thematic approach was used to identify categories and recurring patterns in student comments. This enabled a deeper interpretation of their experiences and perceptions during the professional internship, as well as a more structured understanding of relevant aspects expressed by participants.

Subsequently, statistical analysis techniques were applied to examine both the data from the assessment instrument and the student database. Tools such as frequency distribution tables, bar charts, and pie charts were employed, allowing for descriptive and inferential analysis. Measures of central tendency, such as the mean, were also calculated, and possible correlations between variables were explored with the purpose of identifying significant relationships and relevant trends within the data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Sector in Which Professional Internship I Is Conducted

Figure 1 shows the distribution of economic sectors in which Industrial Civil Engineering students completed their Professional Internship I. It is observed that the sectors most frequently chosen by students correspond to Commerce (27%) and Education (18%), which together account for 45% of all internships completed. In contrast, sectors with lower participation include Transportation (4%), Fishing (5%), and Mining (5%), indicating lower preference or availability of opportunities in these areas.

Figure 1. Sectors where Industrial Civil Engineering students conduct Professional Internship I

Figure 2 displays the distribution of sectors in which female Industrial Civil Engineering students completed their Professional Internship I. These results show a higher concentration in the Commerce sector, with 27%, followed by Education (18%), Manufacturing Activities (11%), Health (8%), and Public Service (7%). These data demonstrate predominant participation in areas with high demand or greater accessibility, further reflecting certain trends in the selection of internship placements among female students.

Figure 2. Sectors where female Industrial Civil Engineering students conduct Professional Internship I

Figure 3 presents the sectors where male students completed Professional Internship I. The results indicate that the commerce sector accounts for the highest proportion, with 27% of the total. It is followed by education with 18%, manufacturing activities with 11%, health with 8%, and public service with 7%, among other sectors with lower representation.

Figure 3. Sectors where male Industrial Civil Engineering students conduct Professional Internship I

4.2 Evaluation Criteria of Supervisors

This section presents and analyzes the results obtained from the evaluations conducted by the direct supervisors of the students who completed Professional Internship I. This analysis details the percentage of grades assigned by supervisors for each criterion for the total student population and by gender, accompanied by an interpretive analysis aimed at contextualizing the findings in relation to the formative objectives of the professional internship process.

4.2.1 Professionalism Criterion

Figure 4 presents the results of evaluations conducted by direct supervisors of students who completed Professional Internship I, specifically in relation to the professionalism criterion.

According to the data collected, the most frequently assigned grade was 7, with a remarkable 82% of the total evaluations.

This grade reflects a high level of satisfaction on the part of supervisors, who considered that most students demonstrated highly professional attitudes and behaviors during the internship, aligning with workplace expectations.

A grade of 6 was assigned to 15% of students, indicating performance that was also positively assessed, though with possible areas requiring improvement in certain aspects of professionalism. Finally, 3% of students received a grade of 5, suggesting basic compliance with the criterion, but with aspects requiring attention to reach a higher standard of professional behavior.

Figure 4. Evaluation of Professionalism of Internship Students

4.2.2 Quality of Work Criterion

With respect to the evaluation of the quality of work criterion, Figure 5 presents the results obtained from assessments carried out by students' direct supervisors in Professional Internship I.

The data show that the most frequently assigned grade was 7, corresponding to excellent performance, and was awarded to 71% of students. This result reflects that a wide majority of interns achieved an outstanding level in the execution of their duties, standing out for the quality of their work, as well as for their commitment and professionalism.

The second most frequent grade was 6, representing 24% of evaluations, indicating that these students also satisfactorily met the required standards, although with some minor aspects in need of improvement.

Finally, 6% of students were rated with a grade of 5, suggesting that although they met the minimum requirements, there are important areas to strengthen in order to achieve better professional performance.

Figure 5. Evaluation of the quality of work of internship students

4.2.3 Technical Knowledge Criterion

Figure 6 shows the results corresponding to the evaluation of the technical knowledge criterion of students who completed their Professional Internship I, according to assessments provided by direct supervisors.

According to the results, the most recurrent grade was 7, assigned to 61% of students. This indicates that more than half of the evaluated group demonstrated solid technical competence, standing out for the precise and appropriate application of knowledge inherent to their field of study when faced with practical situations. This positive evaluation reflects not only sound academic preparation but also an appropriate transfer of learning into the professional environment.

The grade of 6 was assigned to 33% of students, indicating very good technical performance, though with potential areas for improvement or minor gaps in the application of certain content. Lastly, 6% received a

grade of 5, indicating acceptable compliance with minimum technical requirements, but with important aspects that need reinforcement to achieve greater effectiveness in their professional duties.

Figure 6. Evaluation of the technical knowledge of internship students

4.2.4 Work Relationships Criterion

The results obtained from the evaluation of the work relationships criterion, presented in Figure 7, reflect a predominantly positive perception by direct supervisors regarding students' performance during Professional Internship I. It is observed that the most frequently assigned grade was 7, representing the highest level of performance, awarded to 76% of evaluated students. This suggests that the majority of interns were able to establish effective work relationships, demonstrating interpersonal skills, assertive communication, and the ability to integrate into work teams.

The remaining 24% of evaluations correspond to a grade of 6, which, although slightly lower, still represents a high level of performance. This indicates that although some aspects could be improved, these students were also positively assessed in terms of their ability to interact and collaborate in the workplace. The absence of lower grades highlights that, overall, students were able to adequately adapt to workplace dynamics, maintaining respectful, professional, and productive work relationships.

Figure 7. Evaluation of the work relationships of internship students

4.2.5 Initiative Criterion

Figure 8 presents the results corresponding to the evaluation of the initiative criterion applied by direct supervisors to students who completed Professional Internship I. The data show that the most frequently assigned grade was 7, reaching 76% of total evaluations.

This high proportion indicates that a significant majority of students demonstrated proactive behavior in their duties, anticipating workplace needs, proposing solutions, and assuming responsibilities without constant supervision. Such behavior reflects a favorable disposition toward autonomous learning and appropriate adaptation to the challenges of the professional environment.

A total of 18% of students received a grade of 6, which also represents a high level of performance, though with certain aspects requiring further development. These results suggest that although these students demonstrated initiative, they may benefit from strengthening their independence or innovative capacity in specific workplace situations.

Figure 8. Evaluation of the initiative of internship students

5. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the results obtained allows us to affirm that Professional Internship I plays a fundamental role in the educational process of Industrial Civil Engineering students at Arturo Prat University. This curricular experience significantly contributes to the consolidation of technical, personal, and social competencies by allowing students to face real challenges in diverse and dynamic workplace environments. The data obtained from evaluations conducted by direct supervisors reflect a high level of satisfaction with the performance of interns.

Particularly noteworthy are the grades obtained in the criteria of professionalism, work relationships, and initiative, indicating that students were able to integrate adequately into work teams, fulfill assigned responsibilities, and demonstrate readiness to take on new challenges autonomously. This positive assessment of the workplace environment suggests that the training provided by the program enables future engineers to adapt and perform effectively in real-world situations, consistent with the graduate profile set forth in the curriculum.

Regarding technical knowledge, most students demonstrated adequate mastery of engineering tools and concepts, facilitating problem-solving and contributing to the functioning of the organizations where they worked. This evidences solid preparation in disciplinary content, although the results also show that a smaller group of students obtained more moderate evaluations, which may indicate the need to reinforce certain content or specific skills before beginning the professional internship.

A relevant finding identified in the results is the concentration of internships in sectors such as commerce and education, which account for nearly half of the cases analyzed. This trend may be related to the greater accessibility of opportunities in these sectors or to students' preferences. However, this situation poses a challenge for the program in terms of encouraging broader diversification of formative experiences in sectors such as mining, fishing, and transportation, which show low representation in the data. Expanding the range of sectors in which internships are conducted would enrich the educational process by promoting the development of competencies in diverse productive contexts and enhancing professional placement in a broader spectrum of industries.

Likewise, the results allow for reflection on the formative value of the professional internship as a situated learning experience, in which academic knowledge is articulated with concrete experiences. This setting facilitates the construction of a professional identity, the strengthening of transversal skills, and the assessment of students' level of preparedness for the demands of the labor market. Based on these

findings, it becomes necessary to consolidate sustainable links between the university and the socio-productive environment, as well as to incorporate systematic feedback mechanisms that contribute to the continuous improvement of the curriculum.

The main contribution of this study lies in providing empirical evidence of the effectiveness of Professional Internship I as a formative component. By integrating employers' perspectives through supervisor evaluations, a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of this experience on the development of key competencies —both technical and transversal— is achieved. This approach allows academic staff and curriculum designers to adjust pedagogical strategies and strengthen ties with the external environment, ensuring more relevant preparation of students for the challenges of the profession.

As a projection for future research, it would be pertinent to broaden the study toward a longitudinal comparison between Professional Internship I and Professional Internship II to observe the evolution of competencies throughout the training process. It would also be valuable to incorporate the perspective of students themselves through qualitative interviews, which would allow for the identification of subjective aspects of the experience that are not evident through quantitative evaluations. These future lines of inquiry could further enrich understanding of the impact of professional internships on the educational and career trajectory of industrial civil engineers.

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